

EVALUATION OF TECHNIQUES FOR INTERFACE MODIFICATION IN ALUMINUM-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates some selected methods for tailoring the interface (or interphase) in die-cast aluminum-matrix composites. For a series of aluminum-oxide fiber composites ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$), the interfacial reaction layer thickness was varied by adjusting the magnesium content of the matrix alloys. Three methods of interface modification were attempted for the pitch-based-carbon fiber composites (C/Al): fiber surface oxidation in aqueous HNO_3 , ozone (plasma) treatment, and variation of the quantity of potassium hexafluorozirconate (K_2ZrF_6) wetting agent added to the fiber preform.

The quantity of K_2ZrF_6 needed to fully infiltrate the carbon-fiber preforms was significantly less than previously reported for gravity casting; fiber volume fractions of 50 to 60% were achieved. Surface treatment of the carbon fibers led to an increase in fiber surface roughness, but the small quantity of Al_4C_3 at the interface was unchanged.

Shear tests were done to assess interfacial shear strength, but the shear-fracture surfaces did not exhibit interfacial debonding. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites failed by shear of the matrix phase; the C/Al composites failed by shear-fracture of the fibers.

The flexural strength of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites was close to the rule of mixtures despite the variation in reaction layer thickness and matrix strength with Mg content. The shear and flexural response of the C/Al composites showed a marked dependence on the type of fiber used, but little dependence on surface treatment. The mechanical properties of the C/Al composites are explained in terms of the microstructure and anisotropy of the fibers.

KEYWORDS: interface; aluminum matrix; graphite fiber; ceramic fiber.

1. EXPERIMENTAL

The die-casting apparatus and processing method used to prepare $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites has been described previously (1). The significant variables were as follows: melt temperature, 800 °C; preform temperature, 645 °C; final squeeze pressure, 10-15 MPa. One modification required for the preparation of C/Al composites was the use of K_2ZrF_6 as a wetting agent.

1.1 Materials Selection Three fiber systems were investigated: two types of pitch-based carbon fibers (DuPont E-120 and E-55) and polycrystalline $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ fibers (DuPont Fiber FP). Selected fiber properties are presented in Table 1, below.

TABLE 1 FIBER PROPERTIES

Fiber Type	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation to Break (%)	Density (g/cm^3)	Reference
E-120 (untreated) (ozone-treated)	830	3400	0.55	2.19	E-120 specifications (2)
	855	3503	0.49	—	lot measurement (3)
	814	3254	0.47	—	lot measurement (3)
E-55 (untreated)	378	3200	0.74	2.14	E-55 specifications (2)
	359	3061	0.75	—	lot measurement (3)
Fiber FP	379	1380	0.4	3.95	(4)

The baseline Al-5%Mg alloy used for the C/Al composites was prepared by the Reynolds Metals Company. For the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites, the matrix alloy Mg concentration was varied by mixing the Al-5%Mg alloy with 99.95%-Al.

1.2 Fiber Surface Treatment Unsized $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ fibers were used for the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites. One lot of E-120 carbon fibers was surface treated according to a method given by Bahl, et al. (5). Aqueous HNO_3 solutions with concentrations of 4, 8, 12, and 16 M were prepared from reagent grade HNO_3 (approximately 16 M) and deionized water. Bundles of carbon fibers (20 cm length, 150 tows, 3000 filaments per tow) were refluxed for 30 min in the respective solutions, rinsed with deionized water, and then introduced into the cavities of the graphite molds while the fibers were wet. A second lot of E-120 fibers was given a proprietary ozone plasma treatment by the manufacturer.

The wetting agent was introduced into the fiber preforms by the method of Rocher, et al. (6). Fiber-containing molds were soaked for 5 min in a boiling, saturated, aqueous solution containing about 25 g/l of K_2ZrF_6 . The quantity of K_2ZrF_6 incorporated in the fiber preforms was about 0.5 g/m^2 (mass per unit area of fiber surface) for the E-120 fibers, and 0.2-0.5 g/m^2 for the E-55 fibers. This was significantly less than the 35-120 g/m^2 reported by Rocher, and 10 g/m^2 given by Karandikar and Chou (7), who used K_2ZrF_6 in conjunction with other fiber coatings. These gravity casting experiments (6, 7) involved fiber volume fractions on the order of 15%; carbon fiber volume fractions of 50-60% were achieved in the present work.

1.3 Mechanical Testing A blanking shear test (Figure 1a) used for aluminum alloys (8) was adapted for shear testing of the composite specimens. This test method can be used to measure both the matrix and composite shear strengths, unlike the Iosipescu or short-beam shear tests. The disk-shaped specimens were cut to a thickness of about 1.6 mm using a diamond saw, and then hand lapped with a 600 grit abrasive to remove any surface damage. The cross-head speed of the screw-driven Instron Model 1125 was set at 0.254 mm/min (0.01 in/min).

The longitudinal mechanical properties along the fiber direction were tested in four-point flexure (Figure 1b) according to ASTM D 790 (9). This test method was selected on the basis of the available specimen size and extreme anisotropy of the C/Al composites, which ruled out conventional end-tabbed tensile testing. Rectangular-prism-shaped specimens were cut from the cylindrical castings with a diamond saw; final dimensions in mm of about 1.5 x 5 x 50 were obtained by surface grinding. Micromeritics, Inc. type CEA-06-125UN-350 strain gages were affixed to the gage section of the test specimens; for the C/Al composites both tensile and compressive faces were gaged to capture any difference between tensile and compressive response. The cross-head speed of the screw-driven Instron Model 1125 was set at 0.254 mm/min (0.01 in/min) giving a strain rate of approximately 25 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}\cdot\text{s}$.

Blanking Shear Test Fixture

(a)

ASTM D-790 Flexure Test

(b)

Figure 1 Schematic of testing geometries: (a) blanking shear test, (b) 4-point flexure specimen showing fiber orientation nominal dimensions.

1.4 Electron Microscopy A Philips 501 scanning electron microscope (SEM) was operated at 30 kV for fractography and 15 kV for examination of fiber surfaces. The SEM specimens were coated with gold to reduce charging. A Phillips 400T transmission electron microscope (TEM) was operated at 120 kV for investigation of interfacial microstructure. Specimens for the TEM were prepared by mechanical dimpling followed by ion-milling.

2. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Mechanical test results for the aluminum-matrix composites are presented in Tables 2 to 4, below. All results are presented as average \pm standard deviation. The flexural data is based on 4 replicates per casting; at least six replicates per casting were tested in shear. Figures 2, 3a, and 3b show the corresponding flexural stress-strain curves for the three composite systems.

TABLE 2 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF Al_2O_3/Al COMPOSITES

Mg conc. (wt. %)*	Flexural Result			Shear Results			
	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Failure Strain (tensile face) ($\mu m/m$)	Composite		Matrix	
				Mg conc. (wt. %)**	Shear Strength (MPa)	Mg conc. (wt. %)**	Shear Strength (MPa)
				> 0.001	83 \pm 6	> 0.001	44 \pm 3
1.0	209 \pm 5	765 \pm 102	3800 \pm 540	0.97	100 \pm 12	0.51	61 \pm 4
2.6	181 \pm 9	747 \pm 88	4300 \pm 560	2.17	128 \pm 12	0.96	76 \pm 4
4.8	191 \pm 6	728 \pm 27	4040 \pm 100	2.27	135 \pm 12	2.04	105 \pm 4
				4.06	172 \pm 7	4.82	155 \pm 6

* measured by DC plasma spectroscopy

** calculated from masses of Al-5%Mg and Al-99.95% added to melting crucible

TABLE 3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF E-55/Al-5%Mg COMPOSITES

Wetting Agent (g/m^2)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Failure Strain ($\mu m/m$)	Shear Strength (MPa)
0.19	230 \pm 26	881 \pm 125	4110 \pm 670	76 \pm 22
0.31	246 \pm 18	626 \pm 46	2660 \pm 340	80 \pm 12
0.44	252 \pm 30	878 \pm 130	3590 \pm 320	88 \pm 15

TABLE 4 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF E-120/Al-5%Mg COMPOSITES

Surface Treatment	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Tensile Face Failure Strain ($\mu m/m$)	Shear Strength (MPa)
untreated, as-received	*	*	*	37 \pm 10
oxidized in 4 M HNO_3 (aq)	435 \pm 51	849 \pm 45	2990 \pm 220	31 \pm 5
oxidized in 8 M HNO_3 (aq)	439 \pm 27	818 \pm 60	2920 \pm 430	37 \pm 7
oxidized in 12 M HNO_3 (aq)	449 \pm 28	897 \pm 31	3310 \pm 220	27 \pm 11
oxidized in 16 M HNO_3 (aq)	*	*	*	19.2 \pm 1.6
ozone (plasma) treated	438 \pm 30	719 \pm 26	2185 \pm 74	21.3 \pm 7.0

* not tested in flexure

Figure 2 Flexural stress-strain curve for a typical $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-5\%Mg}$ composite. The apparent flexural modulus were calculated by linear regression of stress vs. tensile face microstrain data for the linear portion of the curve, indicated with the solid circles.

Figure 3 Flexural stress-strain curves for the C/Al composites showing differing degrees of non-linearity for E-55 fibers (a) and E-120 fibers (b). Both materials exhibit distinctly different behavior in tension and compression, but the difference is greater for the E-120 fibers. The apparent flexural moduli were calculated by linear regression of stress vs. tensile face microstrain data for the linear portion of the respective curves, indicated with solid circles.

3. MICROSTRUCTURE AND FRACTOGRAPHY

3.1 Fiber Surface Morphology SEM micrographs showing the effect of surface treatment on the E-120 fibers are presented below in Figure 4. The surface of an untreated fiber is compared to that of a fiber refluxed for 30 min in 16 M HNO_3 . The surface-treated fiber shows a deepening of the axially-oriented furrows in the fiber surface, the dimensions of which are consistent with the quasi-radial, folded-sheet structure apparent on the fiber ends. No increase in surface roughness was observed for the ozone-plasma-treated E-120 fibers, which were indistinguishable from the untreated fibers at a magnification of 5000X.

Figure 4 SEM micrographs comparing the surface morphology of the untreated E-120 fibers (a) with fibers refluxed 30 min. in 16 M HNO_3 (b).

3.2 Interfacial Microstructure The extent of reaction product formation in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites varied systematically with the matrix alloy Mg concentration (1), ranging from isolated crystallites for the Al-1%Mg alloy to complete coverage by a 500 nm layer for the Al-5%Mg alloy. The Mg:Al ratio found by obtained by energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy was consistent with that of spinel, MgAl_2O_4 , as noted by Mehrabian, et al., (10).

Isolated Al_4C_3 crystallites were found at the interface in the C/Al composites, but the typical interphase region in these materials was free of Al_4C_3 . The quantity of reaction product did not vary significantly with the fiber surface treatments. Clusters of fine crystallites containing Zr and K were observed infrequently in an otherwise single-phase matrix; no excess of Al_4C_3 or local fiber degradation was associated with these apparent by-products of the wetting agent.

Figure 5 TEM micrograph of the interface in an E-120/Al-5%Mg composite, showing a cracked fiber adjacent to an hexagonal Al_4C_3 platelet.

The morphology of the Al_4C_3 phase showed a significant dependence on the type of carbon fiber. Hexagonal platelets of Al_4C_3 predominated in the E-120/Al-5%Mg composites; thinner, rod-like Al_4C_3 crystallites were found interspersed with platelets for the E-55/Al-5%Mg materials. An Al_4C_3 platelet at the interface with an E-120 fiber is shown in Figure 5, above; the crack suggests that stress concentration may be the mechanism of strength degradation which has been attributed to excessive Al_4C_3 formation in C/Al composites (11).

3.3 Fracture Surfaces Shear-fracture of the Al_2O_3 /Al composites occurred in the matrix phase (1). The shear-fracture surfaces showed little evidence that interfacial debonding played a significant role in the fracture process. The Al_2O_3 /Al-x%Mg shear strengths were slightly greater than the respective Al-x%Mg matrix shear strengths over the range of matrix alloy composition considered.

Fiber splitting was the principle shear-fracture mechanism of the C/Al composites. The highly aligned E-120 fibers shown in Figure 6a split cleanly; a significant amount of fiber debris was found on the shear-fracture surfaces of the E-55 fibers shown in Figure 6b.

Figure 6 SEM micrographs showing typical shear-fracture surfaces for the E-120/Al-5%Mg composites (a), and the E-55/Al-5%Mg composites (b).

The flexural fracture surfaces of the Al_2O_3 /Al specimens were similar to those reported for tensile-tested FP/Al-Li composites (12), suggesting a tensile-dominated failure mode. Multiple cracks were evident on the tensile face of the beam. Some porosity was evident on the fracture surface for the Al_2O_3 /Al-1%Mg specimen; otherwise there was no systematic difference in fracture surface morphology attributable to the Mg content of the matrix alloy.

The flexural fracture surface of the C/Al composites (Figure 7) shows a clear distinction between tensile and compressive sides of the specimen. The main difference between composites containing E-120 and E-55 fibers was on the compressive side; both materials showed regions of macroscopic shear inclined at about 45 degrees to the fiber direction. The

E-120 fibers in these regions showed splitting and kinking (Figure 8); the same regions for the E-55/Al-5%Mg composites were flat. Transverse cracks were found on the compressive side for both fiber types, but shear cracking at the neutral axis was not observed.

Figure 7 E-120/Al-5%Mg flexure specimens: low-magnification view (a) and detail (b) showing multiple transverse cracking on compressive side.

Figure 8 Compressive failure modes for C/Al flexure specimens containing E-120 and E-55 fibers: (a) detail from Figure 3.2b showing multiple kinking of E-120 fibers, and (b) showing transverse cracking, but no kinking.

4. DISCUSSION

In general, the composite mechanical properties were found to be independent of the interfacial tailoring variables. The shear-fracture surfaces of the aluminum-matrix composites did not exhibit interfacial debonding; therefore, only indirect conclusions can be drawn about the interfacial shear strength from the composite shear data.

4.1 Discussion of Shear Results The effect of matrix alloy Mg concentration on $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composite shear strength was discussed previously (1). The shear strengths of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-x}\%\text{Mg}$ composites were slightly greater than the shear strengths of the respective $\text{Al-x}\%\text{Mg}$ alloys; both increased with increasing magnesium content. This was explained by estimating the effective area of the fiber-containing shear-fracture surface. Composite shear strengths calculated using the effective area agreed well with the matrix shear strength for the range of Mg concentration investigated. Taking into consideration the absence of interfacial debonding on the shear-fracture surfaces, it was concluded that the interfacial shear strength was equal to or greater than the respective matrix shear strengths.

Extensive fiber splitting was observed on the shear-fracture surfaces of the C/Al composites. The average shear strength of the E-55/Al-5%Mg composites (81 MPa) was more than twice that of the E-120/Al-5%Mg composites (34.5 MPa), but the composite shear strengths were significantly lower than that of the Al-5%Mg matrix alloy (155 MPa). The difference in fiber shear strength correlates with the fiber texture; the microstructural disorder and misalignment of the E-55 fibers may result in better shear strength. The fiber debris present on the E-55 fiber shear-fracture surfaces is clearly suggestive of increased work of fracture relative to the clean surfaces observed for the highly oriented E-120 fibers.

Regarding the interfacial shear strength of the C/Al composites, the only reasonable inference is that it exceeds the fiber shear strength. It is possible that the effect of varied surface treatment on the interfacial shear strength is masked by the low fiber shear strengths, but the lack of systematic effects on the extent of Al_4C_3 formation and flexural strength suggests otherwise. The high degree of crystallinity of the pitch-based carbon fibers may render them less amenable to surface treatment than was found for the PAN-based fibers by Bahl, et al. (5).

4.2 Discussion of Flexural Results The flexural strength of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites was close to the rule of mixtures despite the variation in reaction layer thickness and matrix strength with Mg content. The flexural stress-strain curves of the C/Al composites exhibited significant non-linearity and different behavior in tension and compression. The differing behavior of the composites containing E-120 and E-55 fibers can be explained by considering differences between the tensile and compressive behavior of these fibers. Two factors were neglected in the analysis; the residual stress state of the matrix phase was assumed to be the same for both fiber types because the difference between fiber and matrix thermoelastic properties is large enough that the stress state should be past the yield point. Mid-plane shear of the flexure specimens was neglected because shear-cracking was not observed on the fracture surfaces.

Several investigators have observed that carbon fibers stiffen with increasing strain (13). This occurs because the basal planes of the initially misaligned graphite fibrils become aligned with the fiber axis as the fiber is strained. Because the initial fiber stiffness also depends on the degree of orientation of these fibrils, the extent of this strain-induced stiffening should correlate with fiber stiffness.

Figure 4a shows hypothetical tensile stress-strain curves for the E-120 and E-55 fibers constructed from the manufacturer's stiffness, strength, and strain to failure data. The E-55 fiber evidently stiffens with increasing strain, but the E-120 fiber exhibits a more typical yielding behavior. This phenomena may explain in part the differing degree of non-linearity that is apparent in the C/Al stress-strain curves.

Figure 9 Fiber mechanical properties: (a) hypothetical tensile stress-strain curves; (b) relationship between axial stiffness and compressive strength.

The compressive behavior of pitch-based carbon fibers was recently investigated by Crasto and Anderson (14), who presented data for DuPont E-35, E-75, and E-105 fibers. These data are re-plotted in Figure 4b, above. If the trend holds true for the fibers used in the present study, the compressive strengths and failure strains can be estimated (Table 5). The low compressive failure strain estimated for the E-120 fibers may explain the large difference between tensile and compressive strain response for the E-120/Al-5%Mg composites.

TABLE 5 ESTIMATED FIBER COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES

Fiber Type	Stiffness (GPa)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Fiber Compressive Failure Strain ($\mu\text{m/m}$)
E-120	855	700	820
E-55	359	1000	2785

5. CONCLUSION

Die-cast C/Al composites were prepared by combining elements of squeeze-casting and gravity casting. The amount of K_2ZrF_6 needed for complete infiltration was much smaller than that required for gravity casting. Similarly, the final squeeze pressure of 10-15 MPa was much

smaller than 100 MPa reported for squeeze-cast C/Al composites fabricated without the use of a wetting agent (12). This method of fabrication offers the possibility that both chemical and mechanical sources of fiber degradation can be avoided in the processing of C/Al composites.

The mechanical properties of these composites did not show a dependence on interfacial tailoring variables, despite microstructural evidence showing a variation in reaction layer thickness in the Al₂O₃/Al composites and surface roughening of the pitch-based carbon fibers. Isolated Al₄C₃ crystallites were found at the interface in the as-fabricated C/Al composites, but the extent of reaction product formation was far short of the continuous reaction layer observed in the Al₂O₃/Al composites.

The Al₂O₃/Al composites exhibited essentially linear stress-strain response; the flexural fracture modes were tensile-dominated. Flexural strengths were close to the ROM predictions. The C/Al composites exhibited non-linear stress-strain behavior; the flexural strengths were controlled by the compressive strength of the fibers. The tensile-face failure strains of the composites were somewhat lower than those reported for the fibers; microstructural evidence of the strength limiting role of Al₄C₃ was presented.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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7. REFERENCES

- 1) W.D. Johnston and I.G. Greenfield, "Effect of Magnesium Concentration on the Shear Strength of Unidirectional Alpha-Alumina/Aluminum Composites", in Cast Reinforced Metal Composites, S.G. Fishman, and A.K.Dhingra, ed., ASM International, 1988, pp. 335-340.
- 2) Ultra High Modulus Carbon Fiber: DuPont PRD-172, Technical Specifications for E-120 and E-55 fibers, E.I. DuPont de Nemours & Co., Inc., 1989.
- 3) Personal communication, E. Schulz, DuPont Experimental Station, July 10, 1990.
- 4) A.K. Dhingra, "Alumina Fiber FP", Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. A, 294, pp. 411-17, (1980).
- 5) O.P. Bahl, et al., "Effects of Surface Treatment on the Properties of Carbon Fibers", Polymer Engineering and Science, 24, (7), pp. 455-459, (1984).
- 6) J.P. Rocher, J.M.Quenisset, R. Naslain, "Wetting Improvement of Carbon or Silicon Carbide by Aluminium Alloys Based on a K₂ZrF₆ Surface Treatment: Application to Composite Material Casting", J. Mat. Sci., 24, pp. 2697-2703, (1989).

- 7) P.G. Karandikar, and T.-W. Chou, "Manufacturing of C/Al Composites by Gravity Infiltration and Their Characterization", in Fundamental Relationships Between Microstructure & Mechanical Properties of Metal-Matrix Composites, P.K. Liaw, and M.N. Gungor, ed., The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society, 1990, pp. 59-69.
- 8) Metals Handbook, 9th Ed., Vol. 8, Mechanical Testing, ASM, pp. 64-5, (1985).
- 9) ASTM D 790M, "Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials", ASTM, (1984).
- 10) B.F. Quigley, G.J. Abbaschian, R. Wunderlin, and R. Mehrabian, "A Method for Fabrication of Aluminum-Alumina Composites", Met. Trans. A, **13A**, 93-100, (1982).
- 11) J.A. Cornie, et al., "Processing of Metal and Ceramic Matrix Composites", Ceramic Bulletin, **65** (2), 293-304, (1986).
- 12) A.R. Champion, et al., "Fiber FP Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites", in Proceedings of the 1978 International Conference on Composite Materials, TMS-AIME, 1978, pp. 225-230.
- 12) A.P. Diwanji and I.W. Hall, "Effect of Manufacturing Variables on the Structure and Properties of Squeeze-Cast C/Al MMC's", in Cast Reinforced Metal Composites, S.G. Fishman, and A.K.Dhingra, ed., ASM International, 1988, pp. 225-230.
- 13) M.S. Dresselhaus, G. Dresselhaus, Graphite Fibers and Filaments, New York: Springer-Verlag, p. 125, 1988.
- 14) A.S. Crasto and D.P. Anderson, "Correlation of Structure and Compression Strength in Pitch-Based Graphite Fibers", in Proceedings of the American Society for Composites: Fifth Technical Conference, East Lansing, Michigan, 1990, pp. 809-818.